

Economic Profile of Buxar District

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Abstract;

Bihar is a landlocked state located on the eastern part of India midway between West Bengal in the east and Uttar Pradesh in the west. The state is bounded by Nepal in the north and Jharkhand in the South. The state is linked with ancient culture of the country. The state has fertile farmland Lush orchards, rich civilization and exquisite scenic beauty. The state covers area of 94163.00 sq km and has a population of 10,38,04,637 (census 2011). Bihar is predominantly a rural state with more than 88% of its population living in villages (census 2011). The key for the overall development of the state economy is agriculture. It is the backbone of Bihar economy with 81% of workforce and generating nearly 42% of the State Domestic product. In Bihar, Labour movement has predominantly been from rural to urban areas. The rural population, mainly small land holders and landless agriculture labour move towards urban areas in the hope of improving their socio-economic conditions. It has been observed that the migration from the rural areas, whether it is permanent, seasonal or circular has the characteristics that the migrants remain attached to their native places. They continue to maintain link with their families and villages through regular visit as well as sending remittances.

Introduction:

Poverty has become the major concern of India since independence attracting the attention of sociologists, economists and political class people. Government of India gave considerable importance to rural reconstruction and formulated a number of strategies for rural development to meet the goal of eradicating rural poverty.

Buxar district is one of the thirty eight districts of Bihar. Buxar district was formed on 17th March 1991. The present district of Bihar, comprising of Buxar Sadar and Dumraon Sub-division of the earst-while Bhojpur district (Ara), came in to Buxar district. It is a part of Patna Division. The district is bounded on the north by

Ballia district of UP, on the south by Rohtas district, on the west by Ghazipur and Ballia districts of UP and on the east by Bhojpur district. It is situated on river Ganga. The important rivers flowing through the district are Ganga, Thora, Dharmavati and Karamnasa. The Ganga forms the northern boundary of the district while river Karamnasa joins the Ganga near Chousa. It is the gateway of Uttar Pradesh. Buxar district consists of two sub-division and Eleven blocks. Of the Eleven Blocks, Seven are in Dumraon sub-division while four in Buxar Sadar Sub-division. All the Blocks and the towns of the district are distributed within the Sub-division as Table no. 1

Table 1

	Name of the Sub-division	Name of Blocks	Name of Towns
A)	Buxar	A- Buxar B- Itarhi C-Chousa D-Rajpur	A-Buxar (Municipality)
B)	Dumraon	A-Dumraon B- Nawagar C-Brahampur D- Kesath E-Chakki F-Chougain G-Simri	A-Dumraon (Municipality)

(Source-Collectorate Office, Buxar)

Buxar district has got almost plain which is suitable for agriculture. There is a one big river Ganga and other small river chousa which are helpful for irrigation in the agriculture. Buxar district occupies an area of 1703 sq.km.

The climate of the Buxar district is moderate. The hot weather begins from the middle of March when hot westerly winds begin to blow

during the day. The month of April and May are extremely hot, normally the monsoon sets in by the third week of June and continuous with intermission till the end of September. The cold weather begins from the month of November and lasts till the beginning of March. January is the coldest month when the temperature comes down as low as 10°C. From the month of April, till the break of monsoon,

the district experiences occasional thunder storms also.

Agriculture is the main occupation of the majority of people of Buxar district. It is an effort to compile Socio-economic information of the district which are helpful in formulating developmental policies for the district and to assess the sector wise requirement of fund to implement the ongoing and newly conceived district sector schemes under the overall framework of 12th five year plan. This effort to assess the sector wise requirement of fund is based on entitlement approach. Every economic entity whether it is individual or institutional or geographical, is entitled to certain provisions for economic goods and services and the states will have to take care of these entitlements where these economic entities are not able to take care of themselves. The annual plan document would be helpful in assessing the requirement of fund for 2013-14 to implement the schemes for achieving the overall objectives of 12th five year plan. Annual plans of Buxar and other districts, which are being prepared would be helpful in schemes/projects and district wise allocation of plan are not at state level. Planning is a process of formulating a road map of policies and actions to achieve stated objectives within a time frame with a given amount of resources. It involves proper understanding of ground realities, setting goals based on these realities, formulate policies to meet these goals, mobilising and allocating resources to achieve the stated objectives. Overall, objectives of planning to enhance socio-economic opportunities for the people by increase in the overall production of economic goods and services. This increase in the production of goods and services can be termed as economic growth. Planning objective is to achieve this economic growth with distributive Justice. District planning is a type of area based planning in a decentralized planning framework which keeps the stated objectives in view. The broader objectives of the district planning are following. These are:-

- (a) Increasing the overall productivity of the district.
- (b) Alleviation of poverty
- (c) Minimizing the rate of unemployment.
- (d) Meeting the basic needs like food, shelter and clothing of the people.
- (e) Universalisation of elementary education and
- (f)

Access to health facilities for all. The district planning has taken into account the resources available at district level requirement of fund to meet the stated objectives.

Buxar district constraints associated in the way of great output realization and to capture the plan requirements ia consultative meeting was organised at district level, involving government officials from different departments, NGO representatives, academicians and people's representatives, PRI members etc. A brief presentation was made before the members on the context of the district planning, key information requirements for the planning and overall strategy to be adopted in the process. Members discussed on the present district situation from different development context. Various issue of the district were discussed and presented by members during the open house session. Their suggestions were taken in to consideration and incorporated in the overall design for preparing the district plan. Based on inputs received from feedbacks and discussion during district consultative workshop, different line department of the district prepared their workshop and assessed the requirement of fund to implement this work plan. This plan was prepared on the basis of secondary data. All the line departments of the district and District statistical office provided socio-economic data which were required for preparation of these documents. Secondary data received from different sources were used to write the introductory portion of this document. People of Buxar district derive their livelihood from agricultural pursuits. The forest of Buxar district is very thin to deforestation, common trees are mango, seasm, mahua, bamboo etc. A type of long grass called Jhalas grown in the Diara area of river Ganga. Jhalas straw is used as fodder and for making thatched roofs. Firewood is the most important forest product. Minerals resources of Buxar is negligible. Buxar and Dumraon have important wholesale markets. The main commodities exported are rice, paddy, gur, mango, vegetable, fish and manufactured goods of Buxar central Jail such as carpets, furniture etc. and the main imports are engineering goods, medicine etc. It shows in Table no.-2

Sources: Directorate of Economics and Statistics, Govt. of Bihar

Major industries includes metal, engineering and agriculture, potential areas for service institute etc. Potential for new micro, small and medium enterprised (MSME's) : rice mill, automobile, repairing workshop, packaged drinking water, food processing industries like jam, Jelly, murabba, pickles, sauces etc. Rice and oil mills are the main Industries. Buxar district has clusters of

rice mill, brass utensils, singhora udyog cluster, printing press and STD booth.

In Buxar district, the registered industrial units are 1448. Registered medium and large units are nill. Estimated average no. of daily workers employed in small scale industries are 2400. Now we explain the existing micro and small enterprises and Artisan Units in Table no. 3

Table No. 3

NIC Code No.	Types of Industry	No. of Units	Investment (Lakh Rs.)	Employment
20	Agro Based	123	4785.35	996
22	Soda water	12	19	–
23	Cotton Textile	10	16	–
24	Woollen, silk and artificial thread based cloths	02	1.05	07
25	Jute and Jute based	5	11	–
26	Readymade garments & embroidery	25	25.69	106
27	Wood/wooden based furniture	76	104.9	178
28	Paper and paper based	02	1.01	02
29	Leather Based	01	1.00	04
31	Chemical/ chemical based	10	67.16	48
30	Rubber, Plastic and Petro based	03	0.89	06
32	Mineral Based	07	257.00	109
33	Metal Based (Steel Rab)	37	68.42	132
35	Engineering units	07	10.21	15
36	Electrical Machinery and Transport equipment	04	0.64	10
97	Repairing and servicing	98	34.57	184
01	Others	100	181.25	378

Source– DTC, Buxar

The district clusters namely rice mill cluster, brass utensils clusters, singhora udyog cluster, Printing press. Types of Industries prevailing in Buxar district are Agro based, Soda water, cotton textile, woollen, silk and artificial thread based clothes, Jute and Jute based, readymade garments and embroidery, wood/wooden furniture, paper and paper products, leather based, chemical/chemical based, rubber, plastic and petro based, mineral based, Metal based, Engineering units, electrical machinery and transport equipments, repairing and servicing. Total no. of hospitals and health centres are 240. Total no. of commercial Banks and financial Institutions are 92. Educational Institutions are following:- The no. of Primary schools are 658, Middle Schools are 164, No. of Secondary and Senior secondary schools are 70 and no. of colleges are 15. There are no large

scale industry or public sector undertaking in this district.

Transport Infrastructure in Buxar district is very good. Railway Station Buxar is a major station. Major Trains passes to the station due to strategic location. The district has been fairly rich in road, communication for along time good connects with the State capital Patna, Nearest Airport is Patna (120 Km).

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